

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Update 1 of the Quality and Risk Management Plan (QRMP)

Funded by
the European Union

DISCLAIMER

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS	NL

Quality and Risk Management Plan

	ASSOCIATION	
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

Project Acronym:	DIAMAS
Project Name:	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
Project No:	101058007
Start Date:	1/09/2022
End Date:	31/08/2025
Contributing WP	WP1
WP Leader:	AMU
Deliverable identifier:	D1.8
Contractual Delivery Date: 10/2022	Actual Delivery Date: 02/2024
Nature: Report	Version: Final
Dissemination level	PU

Version History

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
1.0	31/10/2022	Submitted version
2.0	29/02/2024	Update 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section 1.5 from pages 13 to 14: modifications of the composition and role of the IAB; • Subsection 2.1 "Internal communication and monitoring" from pages 14 to 15: the IAB's mailing list has been added; • Subsection 2.2 "External communication" page 17: new information added on the project's website and the Common Access Point (CAP); • Subsection 3.1 "Deliverable preparation" page 18: "29 deliverables" changed to "30 deliverables"; • A new subsection entitled "3.4.1. Internal financial reporting" has been added on page 21; • A new section entitled "1. Ethical monitoring and GDPR compliance" has been added on page 23.

Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EPM	European Project Manager
EQSIP	European Quality Standard for Institutional Open Access Publishing

ERA	European Research Area
ERAC	European Research Area and Innovation Committee
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
GA	General Assembly
IAB	International Advisory Board
IPSPs	Institutional Open Access Publishing Services Providers
MST	Management Support Team
PCT	Project Coordination Team
QRMP	Quality and Risk Management Plan
R&I	Research & Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency

Quality and Risk Management Plan

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
SWG OSI	Standing Working Group on Open Science and Innovation
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

Executive Summary

In the transition towards Open Access (OA), institutional publishing is challenged by fragmentation and varying service quality, visibility, and sustainability. To address this issue, DIAMAS gathers 23 organisations from 12 European countries, well-versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. The project will: 1. Map the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in 25 countries of the ERA with special attention for IPSPs that do not charge fees for publishing or reading. This will yield a taxonomy of IPSPs and an IPSP landscape report, a basis for the rest of the project. 2. Coordinate and improve the efficiency and quality of IPSPs by developing a European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). This quality seal will professionalise, strengthen and reduce the fragmentation of institutional publishing in Europe. EQSIP will serve as a benchmark for a gap analysis of the data.

The Updated Quality and Risk Management Plan (QRMP) outlines the actions to be undertaken during the lifetime of the DIAMAS project to ensure quality of the deliverables (reviewing process) and manage the risks (mitigation measures).

The objective of the Updated Quality and Risk Management Plan is to define the processes that will apply throughout the DIAMAS project in order to monitor the activities, to identify and mitigate potential risks, and to ensure the successful execution of the project. In addition, deliverable review procedures and reporting timelines are defined to guarantee the quality of the work. The guidelines apply to all Work Packages (WPs).

This document also serves as a core reference for the consortium organisation and delivery of the day-to-day work throughout the project and will be updated twice (M18 and M36).

This plan will serve as a guide to both the project coordinator and participants, in order to guarantee that quality reviews will be carried out at appropriate points in the project, and as a reference guide to understanding participants' responsibilities concerning the project communication, deliverables, and outcomes. It applies to all project-related activities, and thus, compliance with the QRMP is mandatory for all involved in the project.

The QRMP includes descriptions of already identified critical risks for implementation, and the description of the organisational measures implemented to ensure the quality management and monitoring.

Quality Management

Project quality management aims to ensure that the current project will meet the expected results in the most efficient way and that deliverables will be validated and accepted by the relevant stakeholders. It involves overseeing all activities needed to maintain a desired level of excellence. This includes creating and implementing quality planning and assurance, as well as quality control and quality improvement.

This quality management plan describes how the project is managed, monitored, and controlled, which methodology will be used, how progress will be reported, etc.

This document is intended to be an internal project handbook that describes the essential procedures the consortium partners will implement for managing the quality of the operation of the project and resulting project outputs. DIAMAS aims to ensure that the activities in the work plan will be carried out effectively in accordance with the project's objectives and adhere to the time schedule, budget, and expected quality standards for advanced research projects.

1. Quality Responsibilities and Implementation

Conducting a project requires making sure that tasks are carried out as expected and on time. It also requires anticipating risks and difficulties inherent to the project as well as those that are external to the project.

The project coordinators have the overall responsibility of the project.

DIAMAS's governance is structured in five bodies:

- The project coordinators
- The Management support team/Project Coordination Team (PCT)
- The General Assembly (GA)
- The Executive Committee/the Work Package (WP) Leaders meeting
- The International Advisory Board

This organisation has two goals:

- setting up a flexible organisation allowing the consortium to adapt to the evolution of the project,
- an allocation of responsibilities at several levels to ensure maximum representativeness of the consortium partners and to avoid excessive concentration of tasks/responsibilities assigned to the project coordinators.

1.1. The coordinators

The project coordinators have the overall responsibility of the project. The coordinators act as the intermediaries between the Parties and the Granting Authority. They perform all tasks assigned to them as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the coordinators are responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement;
- keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available;
- collecting reports, reviewing these to verify consistency, and submitting them in a timely manner; submitting other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority;
- transmitting documents and information connected with the project to any other parties concerned;
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks;
- providing, upon request, the concerned parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the parties to present claims.

If one or more of the parties are late in submission of any project deliverable, the coordinators may nevertheless submit the other 'parties' project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

They are assisted by a full-time European Project Manager (EPM). The coordinators and the European Project Manager constitute the Management Support Team.

1.2. The Management Support team/Project Coordination Team (PCT)

Participants	Executive body: Co-coordinators and a full-time Project Manager
Meeting frequency	Every two weeks
Responsibilities	<p>The PCT is in charge of the day-to-day project management; provides support and assistance to the General Assembly; and supervises the overall execution of the project. More specifically, the PCT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● supports WP leaders in day-to-day management and decision-making; ● reviews reports to verify consistency with the project tasks before transmitting them to the European Commission; ● monitors the compliance of beneficiaries with their obligations as stated in the Consortium agreement; ● informs the project's scientific officer at the EC within the stipulated time frames of scheduled meetings and their agendas; ● controls and updates work plan; ● ensures the timely submission of deliverables.

1.3. The General Assembly (GA)

Participants	The GA is the decision-making body of the project: it is composed of one representative per Beneficiary (1 vote), the coordinators, and the EPM.
Meeting frequency	The GA met at M1 (Zadar) and M18 (Marseille) and will meet one more time at M36.
Extraordinary meeting	At any time upon written request of the Executive Committee or 1/3 of the members of the General Assembly.
Responsibilities	<p>Its role is to endorse decisions concerning the project implementation such as contractual and financial matters, the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the evolution of the consortium. Quorum is reached at 2/3 of voters (i.e. 16 votes), decisions to be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast. The EPM participates in the GA, but has no voting rights.</p>

1.4. The Executive Committee/the WP Leaders Team

Participants	Operational level: WP Leaders, co-coordinators and EPM.
Meeting frequency	Every two weeks.
Responsibilities	<p>The WP Leaders are responsible for coordinating all activities relating to the objectives and implementation of their WP. They also raise and oversee risks which may impair progress towards their WP's objectives and suggest strategies to anticipate and minimise risks. Similarly, the WP leaders implement the decisions agreed upon by the General Assembly, control the project execution in line with its work plan, and monitor corrective actions. Finally, the WP Leaders Team meetings serve as a place for WP leaders to raise issues that may impede progress, or impinge on the work of other WPs.</p> <p>The work plan is composed of seven complementary WPs, each covering specific aspects of the project. Work Package leaders participate in the WP Leaders Team in order to ensure proper coordination among WPs. This team is responsible for the coordination of the different tasks, and is in charge of controlling and respecting deadlines for the deliverables and milestones, the achievement of the objectives, the exchanges between the participants, and the risk management.</p> <p>The WP Leaders Team is the main interface between the project consortium team and the consortium.</p>

1.5. The Joint International Advisory Board (IAB)*

Participants	14 external experts in Open Science have been appointed and steered by the Executive Committee
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Meeting frequency	3 times remotely (the 1st remote session took place in 2023)
Extraordinary meeting	At any time upon request of any member of the Executive Committee
Responsibilities	The IAB assists and facilitates the decisions made by the General Assembly. The IAB meets to provide support and advice on the activities of DIAMAS

*As explained in the first technical report (PART B) and during the first EU project review; to enhance collaboration between the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects, we merged their respective International Advisory Boards (IABs) into a Joint International Advisory Board. This deviation was to create a true synergy between the two complementary Horizon Europe-funded projects that aim to sustain and develop the Diamond Open Access model in the European Research Area and globally. While the DIAMAS project focuses on enhancing skills, editorial quality, and financial sustainability, the CRAFT-OA project aims to create a federated technical infrastructure to support Diamond Open Access.

2. Communication processes and tools

2.1 Internal communication and monitoring

Project team document repository

The coordinators have created a document repository in Google Drive to save and share non-confidential documents created and gathered by the participants. The handling of confidential documents is detailed in the DMP. Participants can be added as members of this shared drive as long as they have an email address associated with a Google account. There are several access levels among the roles of *viewer*, *commenter*, *contributors*, *content manager* and *manager*. New members are by default assigned the role of *content manager*, i.e. they can upload, edit, move or delete files. Setting access permissions requires *manager* access.

The Drive is organised into several main folders, 7 of which are dedicated to WPs and the others to kick-off presentations, templates, deliverables, and earlier documents related to the pre-project stage. Each WP leader manages a folder dedicated to their WP, and the coordinators can create subfolders for tasks, deliverables, and any other items.

Emails and mailing lists

Direct email is used as a common means for sharing information and addressing the day-to-day evolution of the project. Emails can be found in the DIAMAS contact list, shared in the Google drive folder. Several mailing lists have been created:

- DIAMAS team: diamas@groups.openedition.org
- WP leaders: diamas-wpl@groups.openedition.org
- WP1: diamas-wp1@groups.openedition.org
- WP2: diamas-wp2@groups.openedition.org
- WP3: diamas-wp3@groups.openedition.org
- WP4: diamas-wp4@groups.openedition.org
- WP5: diamas-wp5@groups.openedition.org
- WP6: diamas-wp6@groups.openedition.org
- WP7: diamas-wp7@groups.openedition.org
- Joint International Advisory Board:
diamas-craftoa-iab@groups.openedition.org

It is highly recommended to use the mailing lists as a function of each WP rather than sending messages to the full mailing list of project participants. This structured approach to mailing ensures that the message is properly addressed to the participants of each WP and the external experts of the Joint International Advisory Board

Daily conversation platform Mattermost

<https://mattermost.com>

A chatting tool (based on Mattermost) is put at the disposal of the consortium members to ensure a smooth communication for day-to-day task management. The guide on how to use Mattermost was shared during the Kick-off meeting.

The Mattermost platform allows for daily conversation sorted by public or private channels. The platform is hosted by the coordinator and access is available through HumanID requiring the validation of the coordinator's helpdesk. Participants are then invited to join channels according to their interests and tasks in the project. The advantage of this platform is to facilitate daily exchanges or short messages on all subjects and share links to documents.

Topics are arranged by channel in order to quickly find the information participants are looking for. This lightens participants' mailboxes that are already overloaded with topics other than the DIAMAS project. The tool also allows for the targeted distribution of information only to the participants concerned. All conversations are archived and secured On Huma-Num servers (CC INP3 data centre) as this system offers a host of features keeping the private cloud communications secure.

Organisation of meetings

Various meetings are held to implement the project. Due to the number and the location of beneficiaries, most of the meetings are held virtually. For effective communication among participants, the Zoom platform is used by default, using each participant's personal Zoom account. Invitations are sent through the agenda (Google agenda). The agenda and the link to the rolling minutes document are always sent out to participants before the meeting, either by the coordinators or the WP leader along with the calendar invitation. Participants are required to record their attendance at meetings by writing down their names on the rolling minutes document, and they are expected to help take notes.

For the organisation of meetings, the online service Doodle is used to define dates and times of meetings.

At the board level, the frequency of meetings is described for each committee in the Consortium Agreement, subsection 6.2.2 Preparation and organisation of meetings. The notice of the meeting and the deadline for sending the agenda are described in detail there.

Meetings are organised in a similar way for operational teams such as WPs and for tasks when needed. Each WP has the responsibility to meet at least once a month under the management of the WP Leader. WP leaders may increase the frequency of meetings as required (e.g. the leader of the WP2 set up meetings every week until WP2 drew to a

close). The project coordination team recommends always fixing the same time slot (day and time) to optimise planning.

2.2 External communication

Project's website

For external communications, the consortium has established its own website. The website:

- presents all the project information;
- will host a knowledge-exchange hub for IPSP, including databases, guidelines, toolkits, training materials, and translation facilities produced by other Work Packages. Unlike what is written in the Grant Agreement and upon the decision of the Work Package Leaders, the project's website will not host the Common Access Point (an amendment will likely have to be made to reflect this modification).

Communication with the European Commission (EC) and the European Research Executive Agency (REA)

The Project Coordination Team (PCT) is the contact point responsible, on behalf of the project, for the communication with the European Research Executive Agency and the European Commission. The PCT is responsible for always keeping the project portal up-to-date, i.e., regarding communication activities, milestones reached, deliverables and progress reports submitted etc. Moreover, the PCT is responsible for providing any requested information by REA as well as informing the partners about any information that should be shared from the EC. Project participants and beneficiaries are not supposed to communicate with the EC directly except when there is a certain need that has been previously discussed and agreed upon with the PCT. In all other cases, the PCT communicates and discusses any issues with the EC.

3. Management procedures

3.1 Deliverable preparation

According to the amended Grant Agreement, DIAMAS has 30 deliverables, each one assigned to the lead beneficiary. Each lead beneficiary in charge of the deliverable is responsible for its quality and its timely submission to the PCT. After the quality review, the final version of the deliverable is uploaded by the PCT to the EC portal.

WP leaders are in charge of monitoring the progress of work on each deliverable included in their WP with respect to deadlines. The leader of a specific deliverable is in charge of ensuring the quality and relevance of the content. Each WP leader meeting and each WP meeting represent opportunities to discuss the progress on deliverables.

Two reviewers are chosen per deliverable on the basis of the following criteria:

- One of the reviewers is external to the team in charge of the writing of the report. As a minimum, one reviewer will be selected for each deliverable, two if possible;
- The second reviewer is the co-coordinator.

A shared spreadsheet has been created to list the deliverables and the potential names for reviewers. This list can be populated throughout the project.

Fifteen days before the EC due date, the deliverable leader sends the document to at least one external peer reviewer. Peer reviewers have seven days to provide the deliverable leader with comments and suggestions. The deliverable leader has seven days to finalise the last version. The final editor/reviewer will be the co-coordinator Johan Rooryck.

The deliverable leader provides the document structure (using the provided template in the project document repository). The leader defines the content and invites the different contributors to fill in the different sections. The final PDF document is uploaded to the EC submission portal within the continuous reporting process, and both open and PDF versions are stored in the project document repository.

3.2 Milestones

The partner responsible for the delivery of a milestone is defined in the list of milestones of the Grant Agreement. The lead beneficiary acts as the “Milestone responsible” under the supervision of the WP leader. A table is accessible on the document repository of the project with the name of each milestone and the description of what is expected. Milestones are part of deliverables and benefit in that sense from the same procedures on the deliverables described in the subsection above. WP Leaders are expected to highlight the output of milestones in periodic reports.

3.3 Documents formats and naming conventions

File name policy

DI [WP number.Task number] - [producer] - [subject] - ... (_final draft)

Details:

- 1) “DI” for DIAMAS project
- 2) Number of the Work Package (1, 2, 3,...)
- 3) Number of the task (1, 2, 3,...)
- 4) Producer (acronym of the participant: EKT, AMU, MWS,...)
- 5) Subject section: a few words, connected with underscore or dashes
- 6) (Final version mention)

Example:

DI1.1-AMU-collaborative-platform_final draft

Proposal for a status table on top of each internal collaborative document

In a very complex project like DIAMAS, a lot of collaboration will in practice occur in documents in Google Drive rather than in meetings. To make sure that the status and version of each document are clear to everyone – in addition to what is expected from them – at the Kick-Off meeting it was proposed to have a small table on top of each document that details the status, version, feedback required and deadline, etc.

3.4 Reporting to the European Commission

DIAMAS has 2 reporting periods which are related to payment requests:

- Reporting Period 1 (RP1) from M1 – M12
- Reporting Period 2 (RP2) from M13 – M36

Periodic reports are prepared with all consortium partners. The overall responsibility and coordination lies with the PCT. The reports are to be submitted to the portal by the PCT, within 60 days after the end of the reporting period. These reports include requests for payment and must be drawn up using the forms and templates provided in the Portal.

Periodic reporting includes a technical and financial part.

The technical part describes the overview of the action implementation: work carried out, progress, objectives, impact, etc. It is prepared by the consortium in the continuous and periodic reporting modules using the template available in the Portal and submitted by the coordinator, using the EC Periodic report template.

The periodic report must include the following:

- Part A, including the structured tables from the grant management system (generated automatically from the system)
 - Cover page
 - Summary for publication
 - Web-based tables covering issues related to the project implementation
- Part B, including a free text report containing:
 - An explanation of the work carried out by all beneficiaries and linked third parties during the reporting period;
 - An overview of the progress towards the objectives of the project, including milestones and deliverables identified in the Grant Agreement, including the differences between the work expected and the work actually performed (if any).

The financial part consists of each individual financial statement (for all beneficiaries, affiliated entities) and explains the use of resources. The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action. All eligible costs and contributions incurred should be declared, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget. Amounts that are not declared in the individual financial statements will not be taken into account by the granting authority.

By signing the financial statements (directly in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool), the beneficiaries confirm that:

- the information provided is complete, reliable and true,
- the costs and contributions declared are eligible,
- the costs and contributions can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documents that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations,
- for the final periodic report: all the revenues have been declared.

Beneficiaries will also have to submit the financial statements of their affiliated entities (if any). If a beneficiary does not include its related financial statement in a periodic report, the costs will be considered 'zero' for this reporting period but the beneficiary can declare its costs with the next financial report (for the next reporting period).

3.4.1 Internal financial reporting

In addition to the official EC reportings (RP1 & RP2), internal financial reporting is conducted every 6 months within the DIAMAS project. This internal process is handled by the European Project Manager (EPM). It not only helps monitor each beneficiary's expenses closely but also allows us to identify any potential financial and PM deviations.

Risk Management

The *Risk Management Plan* defines and documents the risk management process for the project. It describes how risks are identified and assessed, which tools and techniques can be used, what the evaluation scales and tolerances are, the relevant roles and responsibilities, how often risks need to be revisited, etc. The Risk Management Plan also defines the risk monitoring and escalation process as well as the structure of the *Risks' table* which is used to document and communicate the risks and their response actions.

Quality and Risk Management Plan

The purpose of this document is:

- To outline the risk approach and process to be used for the project;
- To identify the roles and responsibilities related to risk management;
- To specify the methodology, standards, tools and techniques used to support risk management.

As defined in the Grant Agreement, several risks and mitigation measures have already been defined at the submission of the proposal, see table below:

Risk No	Description	Work Package No	Probability	Importance of the impact	Proposed Mitigation measures
1	Difficult management of a consortium of 23 partners	WP1	High	High	Consortium agreement and two scientific coordinators at 20% FTE
2	A partner leaves the consortium	WP1	Low	High	Planned in the Consortium Agreement, Governance bodies
3	Data management RGD compliance	WP1	Low	High	Data Management Plan
4	Low response of stakeholders and target groups to EQSIP	WP3	Medium	High	Co-creation of EQSIP with IPSPs Inclusion of panels in focus groups and surveys Strong dissemination and exploitation measures
5	Late delivery of landscape and gap analysis delaying	WP2	Low	High	In-house analysis relies in the knowledge and competences included in the consortium, thanks to the strong diversity and specific

					expertise of each partner
6	Slow implementation of capacity-building tools	WP4	Medium	High	Tasks stretched over deliverable due dates to anticipate potential delays
7	Low adhesion of IPSPs and funders on the proposed funding models	WP7	Medium	High	Stronger implication of cOAlition S in the promotion of the sustainability tools
8	Inability to design recommendations fitting with the diversity of national R&I systems across the ERA	WP6	Low	High	Use ERA policy coordination frameworks such as ERAC (SWG OSI) to give input

Risks will be identified and analysed throughout the project based on the risk life-cycle processes consisting of risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, risk mitigation and risk tracking. Having a global overview of each task and of each WP, the PCT will be able to anticipate risks. This will be raised during WP meetings and WP leaders' meetings. Each partner is responsible for communicating to the PCT any potential risks. Indeed risks will be reviewed on a regular basis at WP leader meetings.

A spreadsheet listing the potential risks is added in the shared folders and can be populated throughout the project: description of the risk, WP number, probability, importance of the impact and proposed mitigation measures.

The risk table will be updated in the next QRMP (Update 2) taking into account inputs from the shared spreadsheet.

1. Ethical monitoring and GDPR compliance

The PCT works with all the DIAMAS partners to ensure that everyone complies with EU legislation, particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), regarding ethical issues such as Personal Data Collection and Protection. In that prospect, the DIAMAS project's privacy policy will be regularly updated by the PCT and WP7 leader, Andrej Vcron, emphasising the importance of GDPR compliance and the data subject rights: <https://diamasproject.eu/privacy-policy/>.

Quality and Risk Management Plan

All things considered, no sensitive personal data is collected or processed during the duration of the DIAMAS project, and the Consortium believes that the limited personal data managed (names, affiliations, email addresses) does not require an Ethic Committee for the project as it was mentioned in the Grant Agreement. However, a GDPR Joint Controllershship Agreement (JCA) was signed by the DIAMAS Partners. This DIAMAS JCA highlights the GDPR provisions to abide by when collecting or processing personal data, the data rights and the procedure to follow in case of a personal data breach.

Conclusion

The Quality and Risk Management Plan effectively guides the project coordination and management. It constitutes a useful tool to monitor activities, identify and mitigate potential risks, and ensure the successful execution of the project. It can be shared with the consortium for an efficient and transparent implementation of the common project. This document is expected to be updated as a deliverable at M36.